

A New Extension of Shreekant Distribution with Comparative Statistical Properties and Applications

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Abstract-In this paper, we have incorporated a new class of Shreekant distribution termed as weighted Shreekant distribution which has been formulated by applying the weighted technique to its baseline Shreekant distribution. The presented new distribution has been encompassed with comprehensive statistical properties via order statistics, moments, harmonic mean, reliability function, hazard rate function, reverse hazard rate function and moment generating function has been described and studied. Additionally, the parameters of explored new distribution have been estimated by using the maximum likelihood estimation method. Furthermore, the proposed new distribution has been examined and analyzed by fitting a real lifetime data set to demonstrate its flexibility and capability.

Keywords:Weighted distribution, Shreekant distribution, Reliability analysis, Order statistics, Maximum likelihood estimation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The weighted distribution has emerged as a powerful tool in distribution theory because it provides a new technique to extend the existing standard distributions by incorporating an additional parameter to it. This additional parameter makes the existing distribution more flexible. This idea was introduced by Fisher (1934) to study the ascertainment bias which later on Rao (1965) formulated in more general way with respect to modelling statistical data were the routine practice of using standard distributions for the purpose was found to be inappropriate. The weighted distributions are applicable if observations are recorded without any experiment, repetition and random process. The weighted distributions are suitable in case of unequal probability sampling like biomedicine, ecology, biostatistics and survival data analysis. This idea has been used as a device for the collection of suitable models for observed data during the last twenty-five years. The weighted distribution provides a consolidated approach to deal with model specification and data interpretation problems. This concept is most applicable if the sampling frame is unavailable and random sampling is not possible. It has been observed that when an investigator records observations in nature according to certain stochastic model, the distribution of recorded observations will be quite different from the original distribution till each observation is given equal chance of being recorded. This idea provides a technique for fitting models to the unknown weight function when samples can be taken both from original and developed distributions. A magnificent contribution provided by various authors to develop some weighted probability distributions along with their applications from various applied fields. Alqallaf et al. (2015) presented the weighted exponential distribution and obtain different methods of estimations. Ganaie and Rajagopalan (2023) proposed weighted power quasi-Lindley distribution with properties and applications. Al-Omari and Alsmairan (2019) described length biased Suja distribution with applications. Sarma and Das (2021) derived and studied the weighted inverse Nakagami distribution. Gharaibeh (2022) obtained the weighted Gharaibeh distribution with real data applications. Pushkarna and Mustafa (2025) proposed and studied length biased weighted Ishita distribution and its applications. Khan and Mustafa (2025) derived the length biased power Rayleigh distribution with properties and applications. Kersey and Oluyede (2012) studied length biased inverse weibull distribution.

Ganaie and Rajagopalan (2020) derived the weighted quasi gamma distribution with applications. Bashir and Rasul (2015) discussed on some properties of the weighted Lindley distribution.

Shreekant distribution is recently proposed new distribution introduced by Shanker (2025). Some of statistical properties consists hazard function, mean residual life function, reverse hazard function, stochastic ordering, stress strength reliability, deviation from mean and median, distribution of order statistics and moments based descriptive measures have been presented. Further its parameter has been estimated by using the five techniques to estimate its parameter.

II. WEIGHTED SHREEKANT DISTRIBUTION (WSD)

The probability density function of Shreekant distribution is given by

$$f(x; \theta) = \frac{\theta^5}{\left(\theta^4 + \theta^3 + 24\right)} \left(1 + x + x^4\right) e^{-\theta x}; x > 0, \theta > 0 \quad (1)$$

and cumulative distribution function of Shreekant distribution is given by

$$F(x; \theta) = 1 - \left[1 + \frac{\theta x \left\{ \theta^3 x^3 + 4\theta^2 x^2 + 12\theta x + (\theta^3 + 24) \right\}}{\left(\theta^4 + \theta^3 + 24\right)} \right] e^{-\theta x}; x > 0, \theta > 0 \quad (2)$$

Assume the random variable X consists the non-negative condition with probability density function $f(x)$.

Let $w(x)$ be its non-negativeweightfunction and then the weighted random variable X_w has its probability density function given by

$$f_w(x) = \frac{w(x)f(x)}{E(w(x))}, x > 0$$

Here $w(x)$ be the weight function then $E(w(x)) = \int w(x)f(x)dx < \infty$.

In this paper, we have to get the weighted version of Shreekant distribution. Obviously if the weight function at $w(x) = x^c$ the proposed distribution is termed as weighted distribution and therefore its probability density function is given by

$$f_w(x; \theta, c) = \frac{x^c f(x; \theta)}{E(x^c)} \quad (3)$$

Here $E(x^c) = \int_0^{\infty} x^c f(x; \theta) dx$

$$E(x^c) = \int_0^{\infty} x^c \frac{\theta^5}{\left(\theta^4 + \theta^3 + 24\right)} \left(1 + x + x^4\right) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

After the simplification of above equation, we get

$$E(x^c) = \frac{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)}{\theta^c \left(\theta^4 + \theta^3 + 24\right)} \quad (4)$$

Therefore by applying the equations (1) and (4) in equation (3), we will obtain probability density function of weighted Shreekant distribution which is given by

$$f_w(x; \theta, c) = \frac{x^c \theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \left(1 + x + x^4\right) e^{-\theta x} \quad (5)$$

and the cumulative distribution function of weighted Shreekant distribution will be obtained as

$$F_w(x; \theta, c) = \int_0^x f_w(x; \theta, c) dx$$

$$F_w(x; \theta, c) = \int_0^x \frac{x^c \theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \left(1 + x + x^4\right) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$F_w(x; \theta, c) = \frac{1}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \int_0^x x^c \theta^{c+5} \left(1 + x + x^4\right) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$F_w(x; \theta, c) = \frac{1}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \left(\theta^{c+5} \int_0^x x^c e^{-\theta x} dx + \theta^{c+5} \int_0^x x^{c+1} e^{-\theta x} dx + \theta^{c+5} \int_0^x x^{c+4} e^{-\theta x} dx \right) \quad (6)$$

After the simplification of equation (6), we will obtain the cumulative distribution function of weighted Shreekant distribution that is given by

$$F_w(x; \theta, c) = \frac{1}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \left(\theta^4 \gamma(c+1, \theta x) + \theta^3 \gamma(c+2, \theta x) + \gamma(c+5, \theta x) \right) \quad (7)$$

Fig.1.Pdf plot of Weighted Shreekant Distribution

Fig 2.cdf plot of Weighted Shreekant Distribution

III. RELIABILITY ANALYSIS

In this portion, we will have derived and presented the reliability function, hazard function, reverse hazard rate function and Mills ratio of the weighted Shreekant distribution.

3.1 Reliability function

The reliability function of weighted Shreekant distribution is given by

$$R(x) = 1 - F_w(x; \theta, c)$$

$$R(x) = 1 - \frac{1}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \left(\theta^4 \gamma(c+1, \theta x) + \theta^3 \gamma(c+2, \theta x) + \gamma(c+5, \theta x)\right)$$

3.2 Hazard function

The hazard function of performed weighted Shreekant distribution is given by

$$h(x) = \frac{f_w(x; \theta, c)}{1 - F_w(x; \theta, c)}$$

$$h(x) = \frac{x^c \theta^{c+5} (1+x+x^4)^{-\theta x}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right) - \left(\theta^4 \gamma(c+1, \theta x) + \theta^3 \gamma(c+2, \theta x) + \gamma(c+5, \theta x)\right)}$$

3.3 Reverse hazard function

The reverse hazard rate function of proposed distribution is given by

$$h_r(x) = \frac{f_w(x; \theta, c)}{F_w(x; \theta, c)}$$

$$h_r(x) = \frac{x^c \theta^{c+5} (1+x+x^4)^{-\theta x}}{\left(\theta^4 \gamma(c+1, \theta x) + \theta^3 \gamma(c+2, \theta x) + \gamma(c+5, \theta x)\right)}$$

3.4 Mills Ratio

The mills ratio of explored distribution is given by

$$M.R = \frac{1}{h_r(x)} = \frac{\left(\theta^4 \gamma(c+1, \theta x) + \theta^3 \gamma(c+2, \theta x) + \gamma(c+5, \theta x)\right)}{x^c \theta^{c+5} (1+x+x^4)^{-\theta x}}$$

Fig.3: Reliability plot of Weighted Shreekant Distribution

Fig.4: Hazard Plot of Weighted Shreekant Distribution

IV. ORDER STATISTICS

The term order statistics deals with arrangement of independent and identically distributed random variables in ascending order. Consider order statistics $X_{(1)}, X_{(2)}, \dots, X_{(n)}$ of a random sample X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n from a continuous population with probability density function $f_x(x)$ and cumulative distribution function $F_x(x)$, then the probability density function of r^{th} order statistics $X_{(r)}$ is given by

$$f_{x(r)}(x) = \frac{n!}{(r-1)!(n-r)!} f_X(x) (F_X(x))^{r-1} (1-F_X(x))^{n-r} \tag{8}$$

Therefore by applying the equations (5) and (7) in equation (8), we will get the probability density function of r^{th} order statistics $X_{(r)}$ of weighted Shreekant distribution which is

$$f_{x(r)}(x) = \frac{n!}{(r-1)!(n-r)!} \left(\frac{x^c \theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \left(1+x+x^4 \right) e^{-\theta x} \right) \times \left(\frac{1}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \left(\theta^4 \gamma(c+1, \theta x) + \theta^3 \gamma(c+2, \theta x) + \gamma(c+5, \theta x) \right) \right)^{r-1} \times \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \left(\theta^4 \gamma(c+1, \theta x) + \theta^3 \gamma(c+2, \theta x) + \gamma(c+5, \theta x) \right) \right)^{n-r}$$

Now, the probability density function of higher order statistic $X_{(n)}$ of weighted Shreekant distribution is given by

$$f_{x(n)}(x) = \frac{n x^c \theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \left(1+x+x^4 \right) e^{-\theta x} \times \left(\frac{1}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \left(\theta^4 \gamma(c+1, \theta x) + \theta^3 \gamma(c+2, \theta x) + \gamma(c+5, \theta x) \right) \right)^{n-1}$$

and therefore probability density function of first order statistic $X_{(1)}$ of weighted Shreekant distribution is given by

$$f_{x(1)}(x) = \frac{n x^c \theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \left(1+x+x^4 \right) e^{-\theta x} \times \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \left(\theta^4 \gamma(c+1, \theta x) + \theta^3 \gamma(c+2, \theta x) + \gamma(c+5, \theta x) \right) \right)^{n-1}$$

V. STATISTICAL PROPERTIES

In this portion, we will have performed some specific properties such as moments, harmonic mean, moment generating and characteristic function of weighted Shreekant distribution.

5.1 Moments

Let X be the random variable which consists weighted Shreekant distribution, then the r^{th} order moment of developed distribution will be obtained by using the expression as

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_r' &= E(X^r) = \int_0^\infty x^r f_w(x; \theta, c) dx \\ \mu_r' &= \int_0^\infty x^r \frac{x^c \theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \left(1+x+x^4\right) e^{-\theta x} dx \\ \mu_r' &= \int_0^\infty \frac{x^{c+r} \theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \left(1+x+x^4\right) e^{-\theta x} dx \\ \mu_r' &= \frac{\theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \int_0^\infty x^{c+r} \left(1+x+x^4\right) e^{-\theta x} dx \\ \mu_r' &= \frac{\theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \left(\int_0^\infty x^{(c+r+1)-1} e^{-\theta x} dx + \int_0^\infty x^{(c+r+2)-1} e^{-\theta x} dx + \int_0^\infty x^{(c+r+5)-1} e^{-\theta x} dx \right) \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

After the simplification of equation (9), we get

$$\mu_r' = E(X^r) = \frac{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+r+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+r+2) + \Gamma(c+r+5)\right)}{\theta^r \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \tag{10}$$

Hence by putting $r = 1, 2, 3$ and 4 in equation (10), we will obtain mean and other moments of weighted Shreekant distribution which is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_1' &= \frac{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+2) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+3) + \Gamma(c+6)\right)}{\theta \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \\ \mu_2' &= \frac{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+3) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+4) + \Gamma(c+7)\right)}{\theta^2 \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \\ \mu_3' &= \frac{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+4) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+5) + \Gamma(c+8)\right)}{\theta^3 \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \\ \mu_4' &= \frac{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+5) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+6) + \Gamma(c+9)\right)}{\theta^4 \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Variance} = \frac{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+3) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+4) + \Gamma(c+7) \right)}{\theta^2 \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} - \left(\frac{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+2) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+3) + \Gamma(c+6) \right)}{\theta \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \right)^2$$

$$S.D(\sigma) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+3) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+4) + \Gamma(c+7) \right)}{\theta^2 \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} - \left(\frac{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+2) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+3) + \Gamma(c+6) \right)}{\theta \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \right)^2 \right)}$$

5.2 Harmonic mean

The harmonic mean of weighted Shreekant distribution should be obtained as

$$H.M = E\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{x} f_w(x; \theta, c) dx$$

$$H.M = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{1}{x} \frac{x^c \theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \left(1 + x + x^4\right) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$H.M = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{c-1} \theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \left(1 + x + x^4\right) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$H.M = \frac{\theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \int_0^{\infty} x^{c-1} \left(1 + x + x^4\right) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$H.M = \frac{\theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \left(\int_0^{\infty} x^{c-1} e^{-\theta x} dx + \int_0^{\infty} x^c e^{-\theta x} dx + \int_0^{\infty} x^{c+3} e^{-\theta x} dx \right) \tag{11}$$

After simplification of equation (11), we get

$$H.M = \frac{\theta \left(\theta^3 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+1) + \Gamma(c+4) \right)}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)}$$

5.3 Moment generating function and characteristic function

The moment generating function of weighted Shreekant distribution is obtained by applying the expression as

$$M_X(t) = E(e^{tx}) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{tx} f_w(x; \theta, c) dx$$

$$M_X(t) = \int_0^{\infty} \left(1 + tx + \frac{(tx)^2}{2!} + \dots \right) f_w(x; \theta, c) dx$$

$$M_X(t) = \int_0^{\infty} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(tx)^k}{k!} f_w(x; \theta, c) dx$$

$$M_X(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^k}{k!} \mu_k'$$

$$M_X(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^k}{k!} \left(\frac{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+k+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+k+2) + \Gamma(c+k+5) \right)}{\theta^k \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \right)$$

$$M_X(t) = \frac{1}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^k}{k! \theta^k} \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+k+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+k+2) + \Gamma(c+k+5) \right)$$

Obviously the characteristic function of weighted Shreekant distribution is given by

$$M_X(it) = \frac{1}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{it^k}{k! \theta^k} \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+k+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+k+2) + \Gamma(c+k+5) \right)$$

VI. BONFERRONI AND LORENZ CURVES

The proposed curves are used to analyze the distribution through graphically but it consists different aspects. The Bonferroni and Lorenz curves are also being applied in several fields via reliability, insurance and demography. The proposed curves are given by

$$B(p) = \frac{1}{p\mu_1'} \int_0^q x f_w(x; \theta, c) dx$$

$$L(p) = pB(p) = \frac{1}{\mu_1'} \int_0^q x f_w(x; \theta, c) dx$$

Here $\mu_1' = \frac{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+2) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+3) + \Gamma(c+6) \right)}{\theta \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)}$

$$B(p) = \frac{\theta \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)}{p \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+2) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+3) + \Gamma(c+6) \right)} \int_0^q x \frac{x^c \theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \left(1 + x + x^4 \right) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$B(p) = \frac{\theta \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)}{p \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+2) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+3) + \Gamma(c+6) \right)} \int_0^q \frac{x^{c+1} \theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)} \left(1 + x + x^4 \right) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$B(p) = \frac{\theta^{c+6}}{p \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+2) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+3) + \Gamma(c+6) \right)} \int_0^q x^{c+1} \left(1 + x + x^4 \right) e^{-\theta x} dx$$

$$B(p) = \frac{\theta^{c+6}}{p \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+2) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+3) + \Gamma(c+6) \right)} \left(\int_0^q x^{c+1} e^{-\theta x} dx + \int_0^q x^{c+2} e^{-\theta x} dx + \int_0^q x^{c+5} e^{-\theta x} dx \right) \tag{12}$$

After simplification of equation (12), we get

$$B(p) = \frac{1}{p \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+2) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+3) + \Gamma(c+6) \right)} \left(\theta^4 \gamma(c+2, \theta q) + \theta^3 \gamma(c+3, \theta q) + \gamma(c+6, \theta q) \right)$$

$$L(p) = \frac{1}{\left(\theta^4\Gamma(c+2) + \theta^3\Gamma(c+3) + \Gamma(c+6)\right)} \left(\theta^4\gamma(c+2, \theta q) + \theta^3\gamma(c+3, \theta q) + \gamma(c+6, \theta q)\right)$$

VII. MAXIMUM LIKELIHOOD ESTIMATION AND FISHER'S INFORMATION MATRIX

In this portion, we will have estimated the parameters of weighted Shreekant distribution by using the maximum likelihood estimation technique. Suppose X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be the random sample of size n from the weighted Shreekant distribution, then likelihood function should be defined as

$$L(x) = \prod_{i=1}^n f_w(x; \theta, c)$$

$$L(x) = \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i^c \theta^{c+5}}{\left(\theta^4\Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3\Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \left(1 + x_i + x_i^4\right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right)$$

$$L(x) = \frac{\theta^{n(c+5)}}{\left(\theta^4\Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3\Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)^n} \prod_{i=1}^n \left(x_i^c \left(1 + x_i + x_i^4\right) e^{-\theta x_i} \right)$$

The log likelihood function should be stated as

$$\begin{aligned} \log L &= n(c+5) \log \theta - n \log \left(\theta^4\Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3\Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right) + c \sum_{i=1}^n \log x_i + \\ &+ \sum_{i=1}^n \log \left(1 + x_i + x_i^4\right) - \theta \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

Therefore, by differentiating the log likelihood equation (13) with respect to θ and c . we get the normal equations as

$$\frac{\partial \log L}{\partial \theta} = \frac{n(c+5)}{\theta} - n \left(\frac{\left(4\theta^3\Gamma(c+1) + 3\theta^2\Gamma(c+2)\right)}{\left(\theta^4\Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3\Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \right) - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \log L}{\partial c} = n \log \theta - n \psi \left(\theta^4\Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3\Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right) + \sum_{i=1}^n \log x_i = 0$$

Here $\psi(\cdot)$ is the digamma function.

It is quite clear to analyze here that above likelihood equations are too complicated to solve through algebraically. Therefore, we use the technique like R and wolfram mathematics for estimating the parameters of proposed distribution.

To apply the asymptotic normality results for getting the confidence interval. It should be stated that if $\hat{\gamma} = (\hat{\theta}, \hat{c})$ consists the MLE of $\gamma = (\theta, c)$. The results should be stated as

$$\sqrt{n}(\hat{\gamma} - \gamma) \rightarrow N_2(0, I^{-1}(\gamma))$$

Here $I^{-1}(\gamma)$ is Fisher's information matrix. i.e.,

$$I(\gamma) = -\frac{1}{n} \begin{pmatrix} E\left(\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \theta^2}\right) & E\left(\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \theta \partial c}\right) \\ E\left(\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial c \partial \theta}\right) & E\left(\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial c^2}\right) \end{pmatrix}$$

Here we state that

$$E\left(\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \theta^2}\right) = -\frac{n(c+5)}{\theta^2} - n \left(\frac{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right) \left(12\theta^2 \Gamma(c+1) + 6\theta \Gamma(c+2)\right) - \left(4\theta^3 \Gamma(c+1) + 3\theta^2 \Gamma(c+2)\right)^2}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)^2} \right)$$

$$E\left(\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial c^2}\right) = -n\psi' \left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)$$

$$E\left(\frac{\partial^2 \log L}{\partial \theta \partial c}\right) = \frac{n}{\theta} - n\psi' \left(\frac{\left(4\theta^3 \Gamma(c+1) + 3\theta^2 \Gamma(c+2)\right)}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \right)$$

Hence γ is not known therefore $I^{-1}(\gamma)$ should be estimated by $I^{-1}(\hat{\gamma})$ and it is applied to compute the asymptotic confidence interval for θ and c .

VIII. LIKELIHOOD RATIO TEST

Consider X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n be the random sample of size n from the Shreekant distribution or weighted Shreekant distribution. In order to analyze its flexibility the hypothesis is tested.

$$H_0 : f(x) = f(x; \theta) \quad \text{against} \quad H_1 : f(x) = f_w(x; \theta, c)$$

To identify whether random sample of size n comes from Shreekant or weighted Shreekant distribution, the statistical procedure given below is used.

$$\Delta = \frac{L_1}{L_0} = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{f_w(x_i; \theta, c)}{f(x_i; \theta)}$$

$$\Delta = \prod_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{x_i^c \theta^c (\theta^4 + \theta^3 + 24)}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \right)$$

$$\Delta = \left(\frac{\theta^c (\theta^4 + \theta^3 + 24)}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \right)^n \prod_{i=1}^n x_i^c$$

The null hypothesis should be refuted to retain, where

$$\Delta = \left(\frac{\theta^c (\theta^4 + \theta^3 + 24)}{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5)\right)} \right)^n \prod_{i=1}^n x_i^c > k$$

$$\text{or } \Delta^* = \prod_{i=1}^n x_i^c > k \left(\frac{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)}{\theta^c (\theta^4 + \theta^3 + 24)} \right)^n$$

$$\Delta^* = \prod_{i=1}^n x_i^c > k^*, \text{ Where } k^* = k \left(\frac{\left(\theta^4 \Gamma(c+1) + \theta^3 \Gamma(c+2) + \Gamma(c+5) \right)}{\theta^c (\theta^4 + \theta^3 + 24)} \right)^n$$

Hence if the sample is large of size n then $2 \log \Delta$ is distributed as chi-square distribution with one degree of freedom and p value is also obtained by applying chi-square distribution. Therefore the null hypothesis shall be refused to accept when probability value is given by

$p(\Delta^* > \beta^*)$, Where $\beta^* = \prod_{i=1}^n x_i^c$ is smaller as compared to a particular level of significance and hence

$\prod_{i=1}^n x_i^c$ is the observed value of the statistic Δ^* .

IX. APPLICATION

In this portion, we have examined and analyzed the goodness of fit of weighted Shreekant distribution by fitting a real data set and then comparison has been performed in order to show that weighted Shreekant distribution provides a best fit as compared over Shreekant, Rama, Akash and Lindley distributions. The real data set is given below as

The following real data set constitutes the breaking stress of carbon fibres in Gba ($n = 100$) represented by Mahmoud and Mandouh (2013). The real data set is given below as

Table 1: Data consists of breaking stress of carbon fibers represented by Mahmoud and Mandouh (2013)

0.92	0.928	0.997	0.9971	1.061	1.117	1.162	1.183	1.187	1.192
1.196	1.213	1.215	1.2199	1.22	1.224	1.225	1.228	1.237	1.24
1.244	1.259	1.261	1.263	1.276	1.31	1.321	1.329	1.331	1.337
1.351	1.359	1.388	1.408	1.449	1.4497	1.45	1.459	1.471	1.475
1.477	1.48	1.489	1.501	1.507	1.515	1.53	1.5304	1.533	1.544
1.5443	1.552	1.556	1.562	1.566	1.585	1.586	1.599	1.602	1.614
1.616	1.617	1.628	1.684	1.711	1.718	1.733	1.738	1.743	1.759
1.777	1.794	1.799	1.806	1.814	1.816	1.828	1.830	1.884	1.892
1.944	1.972	1.984	1.987	2.02	2.0304	2.029	2.035	2.037	2.043

2.046	2.059	2.111	2.165	2.686	2.778	2.972	3.504	3.863	5.306
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In order to estimate the unknown parameters along with model comparison criterion values, the analysis is carried thoroughly by applying the technique of R software. To explore the capability of weighted Shreekant distribution in comparison over Shreekant, Rama, Akash and Lindley distributions, the considered criterions via *AIC* (Akaike Information Criterion), *BIC* (Bayesian Information Criterion), *AICC* (Akaike Information Criterion Corrected) and $-2\log L$ has been applied. The distribution performs quite fit if it has smaller criterions of *AIC*, *BIC*, *AICC* and $-2\log L$ as compared over other distributions. The following formulas are applied for determining the criterions.

$$AIC = 2k - 2\log L, \quad BIC = k \log n - 2\log L \quad \text{and} \quad AICC = AIC + \frac{2k(k+1)}{n-k-1}$$

Here $-2\log L$ is the maximized value of log-likelihood function under the considered model, k is the number of parameters in statistical model and n is the sample size.

Table 2: Shows analysis, performance and comparison of fitted distributions

Distributions	MLE	S.E	$-2\log L$	AIC	BIC	AICC
Weighted Shreekant	$\hat{\theta} = 8.279803$ $\hat{c} = 9.834606$	$\hat{\theta} = 0.972631$ $\hat{c} = 1.550448$	143.23	147.23	152.4403	147.353
Shreekant	$\hat{\theta} = 1.95629037$	$\hat{\theta} = 0.07559389$	291.0307	293.0307	295.6359	293.0715
Rama	$\hat{\theta} = 1.64336864$	$\hat{\theta} = 0.07405816$	285.8785	287.8785	290.4837	287.9193
Akash	$\hat{\theta} = 1.270694$	$\hat{\theta} = 0.072226$	277.6656	279.6656	282.2708	279.7064
Lindley	$\hat{\theta} = 0.91773148$	$\hat{\theta} = 0.06896156$	277.1388	279.1388	281.744	279.1796

It is clearly revealed and realized from the results given above in table 2 that the weighted Shreekant distribution has the smaller criterion values of *AIC*, *BIC*, *AICC* and $-2\log L$ as compared over Shreekant, Rama, Akash and Lindley distributions which implies that the weighted Shreekant distribution provides a better fit over Shreekant, Rama, Akash and Lindley distributions.

X. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we have introduced a new study of Shreekant distribution called as weighted Shreekant distribution has been presented. The performed distribution has been established by applying the weighted technique to its classical Shreekant distribution. Some of statistical properties like moments, shape of behavior of pdf and cdf, mean and variance, reliability function, hazard rate function, reverse hazard rate function, moment generating function, order statistics, Bonferroni and Lorenz curves has been described. In addition, its parameters are also estimated by using the method of maximum likelihood estimation. Furthermore, the significance and superiority of proposed weighted Shreekant distribution has been examined and observed by

fitting a real lifetime data set and hence it is concluded from the results that weighted Shreekant distribution leads to a quite better fit in comparison over Shreekant, Rama, Akash and Lindley distributions.

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